

Rebuttal letter for the protocol

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This document is a rebuttal letter addressing the review of Chiara Catizone about the first version of the protocol of our research on the Coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals. It was made in the context of the Open Science course by S. Peroni at the University of Bologna 2021-22.

"More context could be provided in a next version of the protocol, introducing for example some references to previous researches on the same topic."

We added two references in the description of the protocol to research on open citations and one research done specifically on DOAJ journals. We included a minimalistic bibliography to introduce research on this subject to the reader.

"Finally, in the last section they mention data visualization, without specifying which kind of data will be used ,as it is impossible to determine yet."

We specified which kind of data we are sure that we will visualize: the data about the citations about open articles divided by years.

"In terms of data availability the protocol provides the publication format of the data gathered from the OpenCitations API. It is missing specifications on where this – an further – data will be stored and there is no mention on how (format) and where (storage) section 3 results will be made available for reuse and comparison."

Following the FAIR data principles the output data of the project will be available on Zenodo with a permanent DOI and at the same time the whole project and its workflow will be accessible on a Github repository.

"An issue here is that there is no strong methodological justification to the choice of using the OpenCitations API (or their SPARQL endpoints) for retrieving DOAJ articles, which could be a misleading lack of information to non-expert readers. For example: what are the benefits of the selected API, do you envision any possible empishment to your work? Also, it could be useful to briefly explain the differences between the COCI and CROCI indexes as well as providing further specification on the approaches used for extracting the data from the API's results."

The citations analyzed in our research come exclusively from the COCI index of the OpenCitations platform. The first problem we faced is how to obtain these citations directly from the platform. The possibilities are essentially reduced to two: either through the API service or through the direct download of the entire dataset, made free and accessible by the platform itself. The first one, after several attempts, has been discarded. The DOIs of our interest, coming from DOAJ, are approximately 5 million. Considering that each request containing a DOI addressed to the OC API takes an average of 1.2 seconds to return a response, it would be impossible to quickly conclude the collection of all the data needed for research purposes.

OC implements beyond the API a SPARQL endpoint, immediately discarded for the same reasons just explained. In fact this system, more dated than the API, has response times much longer than the latter, despite allowing greater flexibility in research.

The only solution that could be reconciled with the search times is the direct download of the entire dataset. The main problem with this option is the amount of data to be preserved on the hard drive. Especially if you try to read the data by unzipping the content.

The choice to focus on the latter method, then, is mainly to be found in the timing to complete the data collection.

“The intentions of the research team and their final research questions have been made clear, maybe the context description could be expanded in a later version of the protocol.”

This protocol serves to reveal the methodology conducted for the research questions mentioned above. Context of the protocol based on these questions however, according to the data obtained as a result of the study and the analyzes made on them, new questions may arise. The study contains input coming from DOAJ and OpenCitations in the format of CSV and JSON. Additional to these input Python programming language and several libraries have been utilized during the process. Because of the amount of citations and the long response time, the data downloaded directly. Further description on the context will be provided and the protocol will be updated when the work is complete. The final version of the protocol will be a guide to the overall methodology of the study in the context of reproducibility.